

TRANSITION STRATEGY DEVELOPMENT AND THE PERFORMANCE OF DYNASTY BUSINESS: A STUDY OF SELECTED SMES IN KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Effective transition strategy development is crucial for organizations undergoing significant changes in acquisitions or leadership transitions. This study investigated transition strategy development and the performance of dynasty business: A study of selected SMEs in Kogi state. The study adopted survey research design. The targeted population for the study consists of the entire registered small and medium scale enterprises in Kogi State with the total number of nine hundred and thirty eight thousand ,seven hundred and forty [938740] (SMEDAN, 2020). These SMEs are spread across the three senatorial districts of Kogi state. The sample size of the population was determined using Slovins (1960) sample size determination formular to arrive at a sample size of 400. The study adopted multiple regression to analyze the data. Findings revealed that creation of continuity plans has positive and significant effect on the performance of dynasty business. It was also found that cultural integration has positive influence on the performance of dynasty businesses. The study further concluded that transition strategy development has a positive and significant effect on the performance of dynasty businesses in Kogi state, Nigeria. The study recommended that businesses should invest more resources and focus on strategies that enhance cultural integration within the organization. It was also recommended that dynasty businesses should develop comprehensive continuity plans to ensure operational resilience and stability. Regular updates and reviews of these plans will help businesses navigate potential disruptions and maintain performance levels.

Keywords: *Transition strategy development, dynasty business, cultural integration, continuity plans*

Introduction

Transition Strategy Development is a structured process aimed at ensuring the seamless transfer of leadership and ownership within organizations, particularly in the context of family businesses or multi-generational enterprises. This process encompasses a range of strategic activities designed to address the complexities and challenges associated with succession planning.

Transition Strategy Development is a critical aspect of ensuring the continuity and success of dynasty businesses. It encompasses the systematic planning and implementation of strategies to smoothly transfer leadership and ownership from one generation to the next, thereby safeguarding the business's longevity and prosperity (Smith, 2018).

Transition strategy development enables dynasty businesses to capitalize on the strengths and opportunities of each successive generation while addressing any weaknesses or threats. It fosters a culture of adaptability, innovation, and resilience, ensuring the business's ability to thrive in an ever-changing market landscape (Jones & Sons, 2021). Transition Strategy Development is crucial for boosting the effectiveness and longevity of dynasty businesses. Through proactive planning for leadership transitions and ensuring continuity, these businesses can adeptly overcome challenges and construct a lasting legacy that spans generations.

Transition Strategy Development recognizes that successful succession planning goes beyond simply identifying a successor; it involves comprehensive planning, communication, and preparation to navigate the complexities inherent in transferring leadership and ownership within family businesses. By proactively engaging in Transition Strategy Development, organizations can enhance their resilience, sustainability, and long-term success across generations.

Dynasty businesses, characterized by their multi-generational ownership and management, face unique challenges in maintaining their performance and relevance over time. Without effective succession planning, these businesses are at risk of experiencing disruptions, conflicts, and even failure during leadership transitions (Davis & Harvest, 2020).

By adopting a structured approach to transition strategy development, dynasty businesses can mitigate these risks and optimize their performance across generations. This involves identifying and nurturing potential successors, clarifying roles and responsibilities, establishing governance structures, and implementing mechanisms for knowledge transfer and continuity (Williams et al., 2019).

Creation of continuity Plans which involves developing contingency plans and protocols that would ensure business continuity in the event of unexpected events or transitions.

Cultural Integration is a way of addressing cultural differences and fostering a shared vision and values across generations. This is essential for maintaining organizational cohesion and identity.

Dynasty businesses have played a significant role in economies around the world for centuries. These enterprises are characterized by their ownership and management being passed down through multiple generations within a family. Understanding the dynamics of dynasty businesses is crucial for scholars, practitioners, and policymakers alike, as these enterprises contribute significantly to employment, wealth creation, and community development.

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Kogi State, Nigeria, face significant challenges that hinder their growth and sustainability. Key issues include unreliable power supply and poor transportation infrastructure, which increase operational costs and logistical difficulties. Additionally, limited access to finance, complex regulatory environments, market competition, and skill shortages further exacerbate the difficulties for SMEs, affecting their overall development and success.

Despite the recognized importance of continuity planning in dynasty businesses, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding regarding the specific elements and practices that contribute to its effectiveness in ensuring sustained performance and resilience during leadership transitions. The extent to which cultural integration influences the performance and cohesion of dynasty businesses remains relatively understudied, highlighting the need to explore the mechanisms and strategies that facilitate effective integration of diverse cultural backgrounds within family enterprises. Despite their strengths, dynasty businesses also face unique challenges, such as navigating complex family dynamics, succession planning, and maintaining innovation and competitiveness over time. However, successful dynasty businesses often leverage their familial bonds as a source of strength, adaptability, and long-term vision (Sharma & Manikutty, 2005).

Research Questions

- i. How does the implementation of continuity plans impact the performance of dynasty businesses?
- ii. To what extent does cultural integration enhance the performance of dynasty businesses?

Objective of the study

The broad objective of this study is to investigate the effect of transition strategy development and the performance of dynasty business: A study of selected SMEs in Kogi State. The specific objective of the study is to:

- i. To assess the effectiveness of continuity plans and the performance of dynasty businesses.
- ii. To examine the effect of cultural integration on the performance of dynasty businesses.

Hypotheses

Ho₁. Continuity plans has no significant effect on the performance of dynasty businesses.

Ho₂. Cultural integration has no significant effect on the performance of dynasty businesses.

MATERIALS

Concept of Transition Strategy Development

Transition Strategy Development involves the systematic identification of potential successors, clarification of roles and responsibilities, establishment of governance structures, and creation of continuity plans to navigate leadership transitions and sustain organizational performance across generations (Davis & Harvest, 2020).

Transition Strategy Development refers to the structured process of planning and implementing strategies to facilitate smooth leadership transitions and ensure the continuity of operations within organizations, particularly in the context of family businesses or multi-generational enterprises (Jones & Sons, 2021).

Creation of Continuity Plans

Creation of continuity plan is crucial for the long-term success and continuity of a family business. The earlier this process begins, the more effectively strategies can be prepared and implemented. A clear plan outlining how leadership will transition within the family is essential. This plan should include detailed timelines, roles, responsibilities, and criteria for selecting the next leader. Continuity planning includes conducting a business impact analysis to assess the potential consequences of disruptions on critical business functions and processes (Smith, 2018).

Articulating the values and vision that define the family business is crucial for ensuring that future generations understand and uphold the legacy they are inheriting. Implementing strong governance structures and best practices helps professionalize the business. This may entail establishing a board of directors, formalizing policies and procedures, and implementing financial and performance metrics.

Continuity planning includes determining resource requirements and allocation strategies to support business continuity efforts. This involves identifying alternate suppliers, backup facilities, and technology solutions to maintain operations. Continuity plans require regular testing and training exercises to ensure preparedness and enhance organizational resilience. These exercises help identify weaknesses in the plan, familiarize stakeholders with their roles, and improve response capabilities (Anderson, 2023).

Identifying potential successors within the family and providing them with development and training opportunities is paramount. This may involve formal education, mentorship programs, and hands-on experience within the business itself. Open communication among family members is vital to ensure alignment and informed decision-making regarding the future of the business. Regular family meetings and updates facilitate this communication process.

Cultural Integration

Cultural integration involves the blending of different cultural values, norms, and practices within the organization. This is particularly important in dynasty businesses where multiple generations may be involved, each bringing their

own cultural background and perspectives. Effective cultural integration can enhance collaboration, communication, and overall performance within the business.

One key aspect of cultural integration in family businesses is acknowledging and respecting the cultural diversity within the family itself. According to Sirmon and Hitt (2003), understanding and appreciating the cultural differences among family members can foster a more inclusive and harmonious work environment. This can be achieved through open dialogue, cultural sensitivity training, and creating opportunities for cross-cultural collaboration.

Furthermore, cultural integration in business dynasty often involves aligning the values and vision of the business with the cultural identity of the family. As noted by Sharma et al. (2014), when family values and business values are congruent, it can lead to greater commitment and engagement among family members. This alignment can be reinforced through regular communication, family meetings, and shared rituals that celebrate the family's cultural heritage.

Implementing strong governance structures and best practices can also support cultural integration in family businesses. By establishing clear roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes, the family can create a framework that respects and integrates diverse cultural perspectives while ensuring the business operates effectively (Ward, 2011).

Encourage innovation and adaptability within the business to ensure its continued relevance and success in a changing market environment.

Performance of Dynasty Business

In many cases, dynasty businesses are deeply rooted in tradition and heritage, with family members holding key positions in the company hierarchy. This familial involvement can foster a strong sense of loyalty, commitment, and shared values, which are often reflected in the business's culture and practices. Renowned families such as the Rothschilds, Morgans, and Fords are examples of dynasty businesses that have a significant impact on the world economy.

The smooth transfer of power and resources between generations, which guarantees the continuation of entrepreneurial heritage and values, sets these businesses apart. The essence of a business dynasty is in the intimate combination of family and business ties, wherein human relationships become critical factors in determining the success or failure of the organization (Smith & Johnson, 2019). The longevity and resilience of dynasty businesses are often attributed to their ability to balance familial ties with the demands of running a successful enterprise. Dynasty businesses are built on a fine balance between family ties and business needs, which greatly influences both their long-term sustainability and the effects they have on the economy as a whole.

Small and Medium Enterprises

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) refer to businesses that maintain relatively small levels of revenues, assets, or number of employees compared to larger corporations (Ratten, 2020). The exact criteria for defining SMEs can

vary by country and industry, but they generally include characteristics such as limited scale of operations, fewer employees, and lower levels of capital investment compared to larger enterprises (Bartlett & Usselman, 2020).

SMEs play a crucial role in economies worldwide, contributing significantly to employment, innovation, and economic growth (World Bank, 2020). They are often considered the backbone of many economies due to their flexibility, agility, and ability to adapt quickly to changing market conditions (Gössling et al., 2020). SMEs operate in various sectors, including manufacturing, services, retail, and technology.

Due to their size and structure, SMEs may face unique challenges such as limited access to financing, difficulty in competing with larger competitors, and regulatory burdens (Ghani et al., 2020). However, they also have advantages such as greater flexibility, closer relationships with customers, and faster decision-making processes (Menguc et al., 2020).

Theoretical Framework

Relay Theory

The theoretical framework underpinning this study is relay theory, particularly in the context of family businesses. Unlike many other theories, relay theory does not owe its origins to a single individual or proponent. Rather, it has evolved organically from the collective wisdom and experience of experts in the realms of family business, succession planning, and governance.

Relay theory draws upon a vast array of knowledge accumulated over time by researchers, consultants, and practitioners in the field. It synthesizes perspectives from disciplines such as management, psychology, sociology, and family systems theory to offer a comprehensive understanding of the intricate dynamics and challenges involved in intergenerational transitions within family-owned enterprises.

While certain scholars may have contributed significantly to shaping and refining relay theory through their scholarly works or consultancy endeavors, it is best understood as a collaborative endeavor—a body of knowledge and best practices collectively forged by the community rather than attributed to any single individual. At its core, relay theory in family business seeks to facilitate the enduring success and sustainability of such enterprises by ensuring the seamless transfer of leadership, fostering familial cohesion, and safeguarding the business's fundamental values and vision across successive generations.

In practical terms, relay theory entails meticulous succession planning, wherein the baton of leadership and ownership is passed from one generation to the next, akin to a relay race. This process involves identifying and nurturing the next cohort of leaders within the family, equipping them with the requisite skills and knowledge to steer the business forward while preserving its essence. Key considerations within relay theory include the importance of continuity in family businesses, achieved through meticulous succession planning to ensure a smooth transition devoid of disruptions or dilution of the enterprise's core identity. This necessitates a concerted effort to

cultivate the necessary capabilities and competencies in the successor generation through tailored training, education, and mentorship initiatives.

Effective communication emerges as a linchpin of relay theory, facilitating transparent dialogues among family members regarding their respective roles, expectations, and the overarching transition strategy. Such clarity of communication serves to align family members, mitigate potential conflicts, and forestall misunderstandings.

Moreover, relay theory underscores the significance of establishing robust governance structures and frameworks within family businesses, providing a scaffolding for effective decision-making, accountability, and stewardship across generations. These structures serve as a bulwark against potential fissures or power struggles within the family, ensuring the business's continuity and prosperity in the long run.

METHODS

This study adopted survey research design. The target population of this study is the entire registered small and medium scale enterprises in Kogi State with the total number of nine hundred and thirty eight thousand ,seven hundred and forty [938740] (SMEDAN, 2020). These SMEs are spread across the three senatorial districts of Kogi state.

The study used simple random sampling technique to choose the sample, this is because it gives opportunity for every item to be selected. This is because SMEs fall into different industries and cluster. In the first stage, the researcher stratified the SMEs in Kogi State on the basis of activities. SMEs clusters were located and surveyed in the state.

The sample size of this population is determined using Slovincs (1960) sample size determination formular. This technique is used to calculate the number of samples required when the population is too large to directly sample every member.

Formular :

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where :

n= number of samples

N= total population

e= error tolerance (level)

A confidence level of 95 percent (given a margin of error of 0.05)

$$n = \frac{938740}{1 + (938740)(0.05^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{938740}{1 + (938740)(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{938740}{2347.85}$$

n=400 approximately

The Slovincs sampling technique was used to arrive at a sample of four hundred (400). A total of 400 questionnaires were given to owners and operators of family owned businesses in the hospitality and table water producing industries across selected SMEs in Kogi state. Qualitative data, including interviews with business owners, were utilized to align various cultural and economic contexts.

The responses to the items on the questionnaires were analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis constructed to suit the objective of the study. The model enabled the establishment of a relationship between the dependent variable which is performance of dynasty business and independent variable which are variables obtained from the coded result of the questionnaires from the respondents. The researcher employed the use of IBM Statistical Package for Social Science (IBM SPSS) Version 26 to analyze the data that was obtained from the questionnaires.

Model Specification

The following regression model was formulated for the study:

$$PDB = f(TSD)$$

$$PDB = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CCP + \beta_2 CI + \mu_i \text{-----} (1)$$

Where: TSD = an indicator representing transition strategy development (Independent Variable);

PDB:= dependent variable representing performance of dynasty business

β_0 = a constant and β_{1-3} = coefficients of independent variables;

CCP = a predictor representing Independent Variable (Creation of continuity plan);

CI= a predictor representing Independent Variable (Cultural integration);

μ = Stochastic error term;

i = Cross sectional; and

f = Functional relationship.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researcher distributed 400 copies of questionnaires, but retrieved 317 copies of questionnaire.

Table 1**Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.844 ^a	.713	.710		1.20720

a. Predictors: (Constant), CCP, CI

Table 1 shows a strong positive relationship between the predictors creation of continuity plan and cultural integration and the dependent variable. The model has an R-squared value of 0.713, indicating that 71.3% of the variance in performance of dynasty business is explained by these predictors. This high R-squared value suggests a well-fitted model, with an adjusted R-squared of 0.710 accounting for the number of predictors included. The standard error of 1.20720 indicates the average deviation of the observed values from the regression line.

Table 2**ANOVA^a**

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2356.330	2	471.266	1832.161	.000 ^b
	Residual	80.767	315	.257		
	Total	2437.097	317			

a. Dependent Variable: PDB

b. Predictors: (Constant), CCP, CI

Table 2 provides further validation of the model's effectiveness. The F-value of 1832.161 is exceptionally high, demonstrating that the model significantly explains the variance in performance of dynasty business. With a p-value of 0.000, the results are statistically significant, confirming that the predictors creation of continuity plan and cultural integration have a meaningful impact on the performance of dynasty businesses.

Table 3**Coefficients^a**

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.306	.117	5.311	.004
	CCP	.192	.071	.271	.007
	CI	.525	.037	14.130	.000

a. Dependent Variable: PDB

Table 3 breaks down the contributions of each predictor. The constant term is 0.306, which is significant with a p-value of 0.004. Among the predictors, cultural integration has the most substantial effect on the performance of

dynasty business, with a coefficient of 0.525 and a Beta value of 0.401. This suggests that cultural integration has a strong positive influence on PDB. The result further indicates the rejection of the null hypotheses. This implies that a unit change in cultural integration will bring about a unit increase in the performance of dynasty businesses in Kogi State. This result aligns with Sirmon and Hitt's (2003) perspective, which suggests that recognizing and valuing cultural differences among family members can create a more inclusive and harmonious work environment. Additionally, it supports Sharma et al.'s (2014) view that congruence between family values and business values fosters greater commitment and engagement among family members.

Creation of Continuity plan has a coefficient of 0.192 and a Beta value of 0.157, though it is still significant with a p-value of 0.007. Also, the result further indicates the rejection of the null hypotheses. This implies that a unit change in the creation of continuity plan will bring about a unit increase in the performance of dynasty businesses in Kogi State. Smith (2018) similarly observes that continuity planning involves impact analysis to evaluate the potential consequences of disruptions on critical business functions and processes. Additionally, Anderson (2023) highlights that such planning helps identify weaknesses in the plan, familiarize stakeholders with their roles, and enhance response capabilities. The relay theory's emphasis on meticulous succession planning further supports these findings, highlighting the critical importance of effective leadership transfer.

In summary, the model is robust, effectively explaining a large portion of the variance in PDB. Both predictors are significant, with cultural integration demonstrating a stronger effect than creation of Continuity plan. The overall significance and fit of the model highlight its effectiveness in capturing the relationships between the predictors and the dependent variable.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study concluded that transition strategy development has positive and significant effect on the performance of dynasty business in Kogi state. The analysis reveals that the model is highly effective in explaining the performance of dynasty businesses, with an R-squared value of 0.713 indicating that 71.3% of the variance in performance is accounted for by the predictors. Both predictors creation of continuity plan (CCP) and cultural integration (CI) are significant, with cultural integration having a more substantial impact on performance. The statistical significance of the predictors and the high F-value confirm the model's robustness and its ability to capture meaningful relationships.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Given that cultural integration has a stronger effect on the performance of dynasty businesses, it is advisable to invest more resources and focus on strategies that enhance cultural integration within the organization. This could involve fostering a more inclusive work environment, aligning business practices with cultural values, and improving communication across different cultural groups.

- ii. Dynasty businesses should develop comprehensive continuity plans to ensure operational resilience and stability. Regular updates and reviews of these plans will help businesses navigate potential disruptions and maintain performance levels.

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